

Three Element Compensated Drum Level Control in Thermal Power Plant

Debyendu Chakroborty

Electrical & Instrumentation Dept, C.P.L., Rp-Sg Group,
Asansol - 713315, West Bengal
E-mail: debyenduc@yahoo.co.in

Abstract : In Thermal Power Plant, drum level control & its density compensation is a vital and critical phenomenon. This level measurement can be done by sight gage glass. This type of control can be achieved by maintaining drum level / NWL, steam flow & feed water flow in adequate ratio to prevent damage to boiler & turbine. This paper will discuss why we require such type of control for smooth operation of thermal power plant.

Keywords : Drum level, Differential pressure Transmitter (DPT), Level state, Calibration, Boiler, Steam flow, Feed water Flow, Turbine, Sight gage glass, NWL (Normal Water Level).

INTRODUCTION

Drum water level measurement is one of the very important and complicated measurements in boilers. Boiler drum level control is achieved by maintaining proper ratio between feed water flow and steam flow. Three element control is suitable for large boilers where rapid load changes takes place. Feed forward plus feedback cascade control is most commonly used in this type of system. This type of control prevents the fear of shrink (water level decrease due to drum pressure increase) & swell (A surge in water level as a result of the decrease in drum pressure) in boiler drum by rapid increase or decrease in water level.

3E drum level control always tries to maximize the steam quality, prevent damages to boiler and hence turbine, balance the steam output with feed water input and compensate for feed water pressure variation.

Compensated drum pressure is necessary because the density of saturated steam and water at saturated temperature changes as drum pressure changes. This type of control and compensation is achieved by a calibrated differential transmitter connected at lower and upper pressure taps of boiler drums with condensate pots and with respect to the normal water level, operating pressure of the drum and ambient temp around the external pipes. The variation in drum pressure is determined by DPT with respect to steam drawn out and the feed water control valve operates to make up the drum level.

THREE ELEMENT DRUM LEVEL SYSTEM

One common application of cascade control combined with feed forward control is in level control systems for boiler

steam drums. "Fig. 1" below show the block diagram of 3-Element drum level control strategy.

Fig. 1 : Block Diagram of 3E Drum Level Control

The term "3-Element control" refers to the number of process variables (PVs) that are measured to effect control of the boiler feed water control valve.

The measured process variables are :-

1. Boiler drum level, 2. Feed water flow, 3. Steam flow

The variation in demand from the steam header is the common disturbance to the boiler level control system.

By measuring the steam flow, the magnitude of demand changes can be used as a feed forward signal to the level control system. The feed forward signal can be added into the output of the level controller to adjust the flow control loop set point, or can be added into the output of the flow control loop to directly manipulate the boiler feed water control valve. The majority of boiler level control systems add the feed forward signal

into the level controller output to the secondary (feed water flow) controller set point. This approach eliminates the need for characterizing the feed forward signal to match the control valve characteristic. Refer "Fig.2" below.

Fig. 2 : Control diagram of 3E drum level control

Actual boiler level control schemes do not feed forward the steam flow signal directly. Instead, the difference between the outlet steam flow and the inlet water flow is calculated. The difference value is directly added to the set point signal to the feed water flow controller. Therefore, if the steam flow out of the boiler is suddenly increased by the start up of a turbine, the set point to the feed water flow controller is increased by exactly the amount of the measured steam flow increase.

If the two flow transmitters are exactly accurate, the flow change produced by the flow control loop will make up exactly enough water to maintain the level without producing a significant upset to the level control loop. Similarly, a sudden drop in steam demand caused by the trip of a significant turbine load will produce an exactly matching drop in feed water flow to the steam drum without producing any significant disturbance to the boiler steam drum level control. Refer "Fig.3" below.

Fig. 3 : Performance of Feed water with Drum level

DRUM LEVEL INDICATOR

Several devices have been developed to notice the steam & water level inside the drum.

Fig. 4 : Site gauge glass for drum level

This can be seen manually via site gauge glass installed on the drum, the gauge glass image is usually projected with a periscope arrangement so that the boiler operator may easily view it. Refer "Fig.4" above.

Because of the temperature difference between the drum water and gauge glass inside water, the level shown by gauge glass is always lesser.

This deviation is depending upon the boiler pressure, piping and the insulation between boiler drum and the gauge glass.

DRUM LEVEL TRANSMITTER

The measurement of drum level is done by calibrated drum level transmitter. The transmitter is a differential pressure type device which measure the pressure difference between high side tap (water) and low side tap (steam).

Condensate pots are connected at low tap for safe operation of transmitter. The output signal of transmitter is 4 - 20 mA which increases as the differential pressure decreases.

On the high pressure side of the transmitter, the effective pressure is equals to boiler drum pressure plus the weight of water column at ambient temperature having a length equal to the distance between the two drum pressure connections.

Similarly on the low pressure side, the effective pressure equals to boiler drum pressure plus the weight of saturated steam column having a length from the upper drum pressure connection to the water level, plus the weight of the column of water at saturation temperature having a length from the water level to the lower drum pressure connection.

Typically the differential pressure range is approx 60 cm with a zero suppression of several centimetres.

The basic idea of installation of differential pressure type drum level transmitter is shown in below "Fig.5".

Fig. 5 : Drum level transmitter installation

DENSITY COMPENSATION

Since the density of saturated steam and water at saturated temperature changes as drum pressure changes, the signal from the measuring transmitter can be pressure compensated to be a milli for all pressure by providing a drum pressure measurement and using it to multiply and bias the basic drum level measurement signal.

Fig. 6 : Diagram of density compensation with DPT

Referring "Fig. 6" and by equation of continuity we can able to calculate the compensated drum level.

$$P_{high} = P_0 + D_w \cdot h + D_s \cdot (H_1 - h) + D_w \cdot H_2 \quad (1)$$

$$P_{low} = P_0 + D_w \cdot H_2 + D_w \cdot H_1 \quad (2)$$

Subtracting "Eq. (2)" from "Eq. (1)", we get

$$P_{high} - P_{low} = D_w \cdot h + D_s \cdot (H_1 - h) - D_w \cdot H_1$$

$$\Delta P = (D_w - D_s) \cdot h + (D_s - D_w) \cdot H_1$$

$$h = \Delta P \cdot (D_s - D_w) \cdot H_1 / (D_w - D_s) \quad (3)$$

Where,

$\Delta P = P_{high} - P_{low}$ = Differential Pressure

$D_s = Sp.$ Density of Steam in drum.

$D_w = Sp.$ Density of Water in drum.

$D_{wl} = Sp.$ Density of Water in Wet leg outside drum.

$H =$ Tapping Difference of drum taps.

$h =$ Water Level in drum from lower tap.

$P_{high} =$ Static pressure at high side of transmitter.

$P_{low} =$ Static pressure at low side of transmitter.

ΔP is in mmWC (millimetre of Water Column).

"Eq. (3)" gives the compensated drum level value.

As discussed earlier differential pressure is higher when the drum water level is lowest, and vice versa. Hence, the transmitter zero must be elevated so that an increasing level results in an increasing output signal.

CONCLUSIONS

Disturbances in drum level are caused by fluctuations in main steam flow. Typical drum level controller, which measures the drum level, steam flow and feed water flow, manipulates the feed water control valve to regulate the drum level. This 3E controller is called cascade control in which a drum level control unit is cascaded into a feed water flow control unit. This method is being used in all big boiler where swelling and shrinking effect in drum take place, we are also having this type of 3-Element drum level control in our Crescent Power Limited, Asansol, West Bengal.

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REFERENCES

1. K. Krishnaswamy, M. Ponnai Bala, 2011, Power Plant Instrumentation, PHI Learning Private Ltd., New Delhi, pp. 64-75.
2. www.powerplantinstrumentationcontrol.yolasite.com.
3. www.2.emersonprocess.com/siteadmincenter/PM%20Rosemount%20Documents/00840-0100-4360.pdf.
4. www.powerplantinstrumentation.webs.com.
5. Installation, O & M manual for electronics drum level indicator, type-2011, Level state system Ltd, Jan 2002, England.